

Gamification and Its Influence on Consumer Engagement

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Abstract.

In today's world of virtualization, it is imperative that every business has an active presence in cyberspace and develops appropriate digital marketing strategies. Staying out of the consumer's mental nodes is one of the main challenges that every marketer and marketing services company faces today and tries to prevent it as much as possible. As a result, there is no way for marketers unless to speak to the consumer in a different tone than the others.

It can be said that the most important challenge of advertising and marketing is to engage the audience. One way to meet this challenge is to use the main human entertainment, which is nothing but “games” that human beings are familiar with from the beginning of the life cycle and during evolution, and have done it in different ways. The feeling of being better at something than the others and knowing that your skills are measured and rewarded compared to the others automatically causes consumer engagement with the performed activity, or even the name, sound, color, and other characteristics associated with it.

A very popular technique in this regard is called “Gamification”, which has long been used in the field of education and has recently been implemented in the field of marketing. Gamification is not equivalent to playing games but means “using game features” to get closer to the main goal. In this article, we review the concepts, researches, and examples implemented, and provide a summary of this emerging technique.

Keywords: Gamification, Digital Marketing, Consumer Engagement

1. Introduction

After the Covid-19 epidemics, people around the world had no choice but to make some of their daily and non-daily shopping online, which led to highlighting digital marketing once again, where marketing costs can be more reasonable than the traditional ones like large billboards, TV commercials, holding events, etc., and as a result, the noise of advertising, can reach the audience faster and on a larger scale.

There have been epidemics in the world before, but the difference between them and the pandemic of the present age -the age of the Internet- is that in this period, being away from societies does not mean cutting off all human communication, but with the help of the Internet, the former routine of life and maintaining communication with colleagues, friends, family, and so on can be continued.

Online shopping has a kind of excitement compared to physical. No matter how much you've seen the product pictures or videos and relied on the mentioned specifications, you will still be eager to wait for the product to arrive, see and touch it up close. So, doing this itself evokes a pleasant feeling in the customer comparing to traditional shopping.

It is easy to predict that after the quarantine experience, consumers will be more inclined to online shopping than before.

On the other hand, the advantages of online shopping like ubiquity, spending less energy and money for comparison and selection, etc., make this shopping method more popular among the low-income and busy class of consumers.

According to a recent study conducted in 2019 among 3500 Austrians aged 18 and over shows that 71 percent of consumers in Austria say they have been shopping more online ever since the country was hit by the coronavirus. Nowadays, 85 percent shop online at least once a month, with most of them making two to three online purchases per month, while 42 percent buy products online at least once a week (ecommercenews.eu).

The number of online stores has also grown rapidly in recent years, and considering the ease of launching online sales websites, will grow even more than ever before. But the question is, will all online retailers be able to generate high traffic and thus good financial returns? Having many similar stores with the same techniques and copied pricing and web design, the same products or services quality, keep this question in mind that what could define the competitive advantage of these stores?

As we know, just having online sales is not a competitive advantage, and paying special and continuous attention to innovations in this field and pioneering in using them, following the needs and desires of consumers, is what maintains and progresses a business in a highly competitive world of online sales.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay more attention to digital marketing techniques and introduce new models and techniques.

1.1 Literature Review

1.1.1 Gamification

Gamification is the application of game-design elements and game principles in non-game contexts. It can also be defined as a set of activities and processes to solve problems by using or applying the characteristics of game elements (gamify.com). Gamification commonly employs game design elements to improve user engagement, organizational productivity, flow, learning, crowdsourcing, knowledge retention, employee recruitment and evaluation and more. A collection of research on gamification shows that a majority of studies on gamification find it has positive effects on individuals. However, individual and contextual differences exist (Wikipedia).

Early demonstrations of gamification emerged prior to 2008 in the fields of consumer advertising and corporate training. The term "gamification" first appeared online in the context of computer software in 2008 but did not gain popularity until 2010. Even prior to the term coming into use, other fields borrowing elements from videogames was common; for example, some work in learning disabilities and scientific visualization adapted elements from videogames. The term "gamification" first gained widespread usage in 2010, in a more specific sense referring to incorporation of social/reward aspects of games into software. Several researchers consider gamification closely related to earlier work on adapting game-design elements and techniques to non-game contexts (Wikipedia).

Gamification techniques are intended to leverage people's natural desires for socializing, learning, mastery, competition, achievement, status, self-expression, altruism, or closure, or simply their response to the framing of a situation as game or play. Early gamification strategies use rewards for players who accomplish desired tasks or competition to engage players. Types of rewards include points, achievement badges or levels, the filling of a progress bar, or providing the user with virtual currency. Making the rewards for accomplishing tasks visible to other players or providing leader boards are ways of encouraging players to compete.

Another approach to gamification is to make existing tasks feel more like games. Some techniques used in this approach include adding meaningful choice, onboarding with a tutorial, increasing challenge, and adding narrative (Wikipedia).

Hofacker et al., (2017) define gamification as the use of game design elements to enhance non-game goods and services by increasing customer value and encouraging value-creating behaviors such as increased consumption, greater loyalty, engagement, or product advocacy.

A widely acknowledged framework for designing games is the Elemental Tetrad Model proposed by Schell (2008). The model consists of four elemental design characteristics that interrelate and create a cognitive and affective ecosystem around the theme of a game — for example, competition, skill development, or enjoyment. In Schell's view, all four elements must be carefully aligned to create player immersion and engagement. The first element, story, or the narrative format, provides context to a game and adds meaning to the consumption experience. Mechanics, the second element, refers to rules and structural aspects of games and is concerned with how success is recognized by reward, incentive structures, and game levels. Game mechanics enable players to know how to maneuver through the game and to form an impression of what is expected and rewarded at hierarchical game levels. The mechanics enable a game dynamic that in turn creates a specific user experience. Third, aesthetics, or the look and feel of a game, instill games with a sense of purpose and strengthen the development of the storyline. For many games, a focus on visual imagery and presentation is important to creating

an immersive experience, although other senses may come into play. Finally, technology pertains to how the medium, in our case the mobile platform, shapes the game experience. For instance, the fact that a mobile device is in effect a networked computer creates opportunities for interactivity and dynamic game play.

1.1.2 Gamification Effects

Gamification has been suggested to have several effects of interest for marketers; for example, brand engagement, customer loyalty, brand attitude, engagement and customer movement (Hollebeek et al., 2019).

In addition, gamification for marketing can allow repetition of the branding message during the process. Compared with traditional marketing tools, gamification has no time or space limitation in branding products or services. Some other traditional media are generally for a one-time propagation so people have less chance to be exposed to the marketing message (Yang et al., 2017).

With a strong interaction, gamification can enhance people's sense of belonging and identification to a brand. When interacting with the system or other participants in the gamification process, users will have various types of emotions and different experiences. This will directly or indirectly influence the evaluation of brand. Finally, people enjoy competing, playing games and winning. In gamification, they can also compete and win rewards as well as revel in watching other people compete. People relish the process of participating in a competing activity with rewards, even if the prizes are small, symbolic or virtual. Gamification takes advantages of the game characteristics and applies them into marketing use. People's willingness to compete and win rewards during that process can be a catalyst to improving their loyalty to a brand, product or service (Yang et al., 2017).

1.1.3 Digital Marketing

Kannan & Li (2017) define the term “digital marketing” has evolved over time from a specific term describing the marketing of products and services using digital channels – to an umbrella term describing the process of using digital technologies to acquire customers and build customer preferences, promote brands, retain customers and increase sales. Following the American Marketing Association's firm centric definition, digital marketing may be seen as activities, institutions, and processes facilitated by digital technologies for creating, communicating and delivering value for customers and other stake-holders. They adopt a more inclusive perspective and define digital marketing as “an adaptive, technology-enabled process by which firms collaborate with customers and partners to jointly create, communicate, deliver, and sustain value for all stakeholders”.

1.1.4 Consumer Engagement

Hollebeek et al., (2016) rely on the definition of Brodie et al., (2011) that customer engagement is “a psychological state that occurs by virtue of interactive customer experiences with a focal object (e.g., a brand) in service relationships”. Engaged customers, typically, display greater brand loyalty and satisfaction and are more likely to contribute to new product

development, service innovation, and viral marketing activity by providing referrals for specific offerings to others.

Mowen & Minor (2009) also state that as engagement increases, consumers become more motivated to pay attention, understand, and explore information that is important in purchasing a product. They further point to several factors that affect the level of consumer engagement, including the type of product, the communication characteristics received by the consumer, the consumer personality, and the characteristics of the situation in which the consumer operates.

The last case, the consumer-product interaction environment, is more important in digital marketing, and the reason for the emergence of techniques such as gamification is the high importance of the interaction environment.

1.1.5 Gamification and Marketing

Due to the rise and popularity of games in marketing activities, the new trend of gamification has attracted the attention of marketers. Due to improvements in the productivity and development of technologies, customers are becoming more and more selective in how and where they spend their money and time. Accordingly, companies are pressurized to find new ways to adapt their marketing strategies in order to attract customers' attention and keep them engaged in the process. The marketing area is highly innovative and sophisticated in deploying new ideas and phenomena, so many companies have used gamification in the marketing area for branding, including earning points, badges and free products through playing games or joining competitive activities. Companies can also take back control of the brand experience by engaging users, encouraging them to join a community, driving active participation, sharing with friends outside the community and even recruiting friends to join the community. Therefore, a particularly compelling, dynamic and sustained gamification experience can be used to accomplish a variety of marketing goals (Yang et al., 2017).

2. Gamification and Consumer Engagement

The author believes that in the implementation of gamification on the website and the digital environment in general, there are important points that can be leveraged for the website and business purposes. Based on the needs of customers, brand personality, and many other elements, we need to find the right game, and of course, after initial research and selection of the right type, the implementation stage requires a lot of attention and precision and continuously needs monitoring and improvement.

One of the first requirements for designing successful gamification is game-like thinking. Just as questions, in designing an exam for school students, must have certain characteristics to be a good benchmark for examining the level of students' knowledge, in designing a game with commercial purposes, a special understanding of how to design a game is required.

The simplest way is to use loyalty systems. This means that with each purchase, or staying loyal to the company in any way, the customer receives a reward. Complimentary, which is used in offline sales from the past or what we know today in online stores as the discount code, is one of the simplest games. The game is as follows that with each purchase from the company (usually in this case, by paying a level of cost, the customer is subject to different types of prizes), the winning customer will get something small though. But this method gradually lost its effectiveness by others imitating in the market. Since the goal is differentiation and making

money through competitive advantage, the company must look for a different way to persuade the consumer to play. Such a way that the consumer considers more pleasure in his mind to play the game and cannot decide between recognizing that the company is looking to make a deal with him or that the company is looking to increase the perceived value of the purchase for its customer.

Another method that has recently been used by some companies in our country (Iran) is the wheel of fortune. Companies like Irancell or Digikala give the user a chance to spin the wheel. A wheel that is often won by the company and the consumer is encouraged to use it every time to get another chance by spending coins or earned points.

This technique (wheel of fortune) is obsolete and probably will not be very effective for today's modern users. Perhaps one of the most successful examples of gamification implementation is the Nike campaign. In 2012, the company used one of the main aspects of gamification, which is motivation, with the Nike + Fuelband smart bracelet and the Nike + app. Nike went to people's inner motivations and invited them to exercise and share their progress and compare it with their friends. At a time, when there were not many effective sports apps available, Nike was able to achieve great success by offering its smart bracelet and designing a simple sports game.

But what the company actually gets through these simple games is beyond persuading the consumer to buy again. In fact, the main goal is to engage the consumer mentally. The more the company's name and brand are repeated in the customer's mind, the stronger get the mental nodes about the brand in his mind, and this is where loyalty is gradually formed.

As with every game, customer seeks to prove his superiority both to himself and to others, whether in the game environment or outside and is tempted to do it over and over again to achieve a better result.

On the other hand, based on the aesthetic nature of human beings, the design of the elements in the game is also of great importance, and in addition to the game strategy, the game maker must also pay attention to creating a consumer eye engagement with the game. Great attention should be paid to the brand personality, the colors that have become the brand symbol, and other related items in designing elements; cause every detail in the consumer's mind becomes a point of contact for the brand.

Finally, it should be emphasized that gamification only means using the inherent characteristics and structure of the game for commercial purposes and does not mean the game itself. However, games can also be used in this regard.

3. Conclusion

With the further development and advancement of technology and its increasing presence in life, companies and all corporations seek to earn money, have no choice but to adapt to the environment and latest new technologies, otherwise they will be doomed to leave the economic cycle. To establish a presence in the environment, which is the first goal of any organization, and to continue the growth and development of activities, it is necessary to use the latest techniques to be able to differentiate ourselves in the minds of consumers from other competitors. A consumer can easily lose interest in the brand and quickly replace another brand in his circle of preferences.

Gamification, a technique based on the earliest and longest-lived human instincts of gaming, is gradually taking its place in the design of corporate marketing and advertising programs and is becoming an iconic method of marketing. In our country (Iran), numerous buyers still prefer physical and offline shopping methods to online shopping for various reasons, but Iran can become a large market for online stores after the Pandemic Covid 19, and much better to make changes to the way online stores are marketed and keep pace with the world's largest economic organizations in the digital market, while encouraging consumers to shop online.

In this article, only two methods of gamification are discussed that keep the consumer engagement with the brand at a moderate level, but countless other methods may not have been implemented by any organization yet, and to discover them, it is enough to use our experience in the games we have participated so far and review methods which have been persuaded us to learn the curriculum or have fully captured our mental attention.

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